

I-CLAIM

**Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe**

Irregularised migrant workers in the UK food delivery sector

Sector report

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Executive Summary

This report investigates the experiences of migrant workers with precarious immigration status in the UK food delivery sector. It draws on in-depth qualitative interviews with twelve migrant riders and twelve stakeholders, alongside extensive ethnographic observations conducted in Birmingham from December 2024 to June 2025. The fieldwork captures a critical transitional moment in the governance of food delivery work—one in which immigration enforcement and labour regulation are being reconfigured under the newly elected Labour government.

Food delivery platforms have become an essential, if marginal, entry point into the UK labour market for migrants facing legal and structural barriers to formal employment. Marketed as flexible and accessible work, food delivery is increasingly shaped by algorithmic control, economic insecurity, and a shifting legal landscape. The report documents how migrants—many with insecure, lapsed, or irregular status—navigate this sector through informal strategies such as account sharing and substitution, which until recently allowed for a degree of economic survival.

This regulatory space has now narrowed. In early 2025, the Labour government introduced new compliance requirements for gig platforms, including more rigorous right-to-work checks, daily biometric ID verification, and restrictions on device and account sharing. These measures, presented as part of a broader crackdown on “illegal working,” embed immigration control directly into the digital infrastructure of platform labour. The report shows how these developments mark a significant expansion of the UK’s *hostile environment* policies into the algorithmically governed gig economy.

The findings reveal that immigration status is experienced not as a fixed legal category but as a continuum of insecurity. Participants include undocumented migrants, asylum seekers, visa overstayers, BNO visa holders, and EU citizens with pre-settled status. Regardless of distinctions in legal status, workers report shared experiences of surveillance, unpredictability and economic exploitation. Platform algorithms function as both employers and border agents, distributing risk while insulating companies from accountability.

Institutional trust is low among workers. Migrants rely heavily on informal networks, with limited recourse to unions, legal aid, or public services. The precarity of work bleeds into everyday life, affecting mental health, family relations, housing, and long-term aspirations. Some workers hope for status regularisation or onward migration, but most are trapped in a cycle of short-term survival.

In conclusion, the report argues that the food delivery sector has become a laboratory for a new mode of migration governance—one that fuses algorithmic management with immigration enforcement, producing a hyper-visible yet expendable workforce at the margins of legality and labour protection.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	2
Acknowledgments	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Context	5
2.1. Legal and policy landscape	5
2.2. The food delivery sector in the UK	6
3. Methodology and sample	8
4. Understanding the nexus between immigration status and work: empirical findings	9
4.1. Immigration Status and Right to Work	9
4.2. Life on the Road: Precarity, Exploitation, and the Algorithm	11
4.3. Family, Status, and the Costs of Precarity	13
4.4. Structures of Silence and the Limits of Support	14
4.5. The Future: Endurance, Stagnation, and Ambivalence	16
5. Conclusion	16
6. References	18

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1. Introduction

Across the UK, the food delivery sector has become a key site in the transformation of migrant labour. While platform-mediated gig work is often portrayed as an opportunity for flexibility and autonomy, the reality for migrant workers – especially those with precarious immigration status – is frequently one of exploitation and lack of rights and protection. This report demonstrates how immigration status and platform rules operate in tandem to erode employment rights and intensify dependency, creating a multi-tiered labour system, where formal self-employment masks informal dependency and exploitation (Mellino et al., 2021).

The platform economy has reshaped labour markets across the UK and globally, offering new forms of employment while exacerbating old and new inequalities. Migrant workers with precarious immigration status are particularly vulnerable, as they navigate the food delivery sector at the intersection of legal uncertainty, racialised exclusions, and labour exploitation (Piemontese & Sigona, 2024).

This report is part of the Horizon Europe and UKRI-funded project “Improving the living and labour conditions of irregularised migrant households in Europe” (I-CLAIM), which aims to examine the living and working conditions of irregularised people, through and household and intersectional perspective, in six European countries: Finland, Poland, Italy, Germany, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom. The I-CLAIM project approaches irregularity not as a fixed status but rather as dynamic position vis-à-vis the state co-constructed at the intersection of different regulatory frameworks (Gonzales et al., 2019) that encompasses not only migrants without a residence permit, but migrants increasingly at risk of irregularisation due to structural features of the immigration system.

The report is divided into four sections. Following the introduction, the first section outlines the national and local legal and policy context of migration and the labour market, with a particular focus on platform-mediated food delivery. The second section briefly describes our methodology. The third section presents the main findings, highlighting the types of irregularity present in the food delivery industry and their impact on the working and living conditions of migrant workers. The final section concludes by emphasising the pervasive nexus between immigration system and platform-based gig work.

2. Context

2.1. Legal and policy landscape

Over the past decade, the platform economy has profoundly reshaped the UK labour market, introducing new forms of flexible work. However, this transformation has exposed major legal and policy gaps, particularly around employment classification, social protections, and immigration enforcement. As the interviews in this report show, these issues structure the everyday working lives of migrant workers in the food delivery sector – especially those with precarious or no legal status.

A central point of contention has been the employment status of platform workers. Companies typically classify their couriers as self-employed, a designation that excludes them from core employment protections, including minimum wage, paid leave, and unfair dismissal rights. Legal disputes have attempted to reject this model. In 2021, the Supreme Court ruled that Uber drivers were ‘workers’ rather than

independent contractors, entitling them to certain basic rights.¹ But in 2023, the Court confirmed that Deliveroo riders remained self-employed, citing the ‘substitution clause’ – a contractual provision allowing riders to send someone else to work in their place.² This clause, once used to legitimise flexibility, has since become a lightning rod for political debate and regulatory intervention (Worker Info Exchange, 2023).

Efforts to reform the sector—such as the ‘Taylor Review of Modern Work Practices’ (Taylor et al., 2017) and the ‘Good Work Plan’ (HM Government, 2018) —proposed intermediate worker classifications like “dependent contractor”. Yet these proposals largely stalled, with legal reversals and corporate lobbying dampening momentum for regulatory change. In a telling example, Just Eat initially hired delivery workers as employees, but reversed course in 2023 following the Deliveroo ruling, terminating 1,700 riders and returning to a gig model (Butler, 2023). Even Labour’s political positioning has shifted: while pledging to expand workers’ rights in 2021, the party has since adopted a more pro-business stance (Lott-Lavigna, 2022, 2023; Stone, 2023).

At the same time, the boundary between labour regulation and immigration enforcement has grown increasingly porous (Piemontese & Sigona, 2024). A key turning point came in March 2025, when the UK government announced a crackdown on illegal working in the gig economy (Home Office & Cooper, 2025). For the first time, food delivery platforms were required to perform more rigorous verification processes for all riders, including daily biometric ID verification, and restrictions on device and account sharing.

These measures effectively extended the logic of the Hostile Environment into the digital workplace, mark a transition from a lightly regulated platform economy to one increasingly governed through data, compliance checks, and algorithmic surveillance (Badger, 2021; Safak & Farrar, 2021). Riders using ‘substitute’ borrowed or rented accounts now face platform sanctions, income loss, and even immigration enforcement. Yet the structural factors that drive migrants into these informal arrangements – visa restrictions, labour market discrimination, qualification recognition, language proficiency and exploitative intermediaries (Mendonça et al., 2024) – remain unaddressed.

Taken together, these developments show how labour market deregulation, stalled employment protections, and the revival of immigration enforcement in the workplace converge to create a stratified and highly monitored workplace.

2.2. The food delivery sector in the UK

While food delivery represents only one segment of the UK’s platform economy, it has become a critical node in the entanglement of migration governance, labour precarity, and digital control. Of the estimated 460,000 to 750,000 platform workers in the UK, around 82,650 are food delivery riders (CIPD, 2023). Combined with couriers and private hire drivers, they make up a significant share of gig workers – many of whom are migrants and racially minoritised individuals disproportionately excluded from traditional employment channels (Balaram et al., 2017; Gebrial, 2020, 2022; Haque, 2018)

The sector expanded rapidly during the COVID-19 pandemic, but its underlying dynamics have since shifted. While early studies (Balaram et al., 2017; CIPD, 2017, 2023) characterised platform work as flexible, short-

¹ (Uber BV and others (Appellants) v Aslam and others (Respondents), 2021)

² (Independent Workers Union of Great Britain (Appellant) v Central Arbitration Committee and another (Respondents), 2023)

term, and supplemental—particularly among students and young urbanites—our interviews reflect a different reality. As wages have stagnated and working conditions deteriorated, food delivery has become increasingly dominated by those with limited alternatives: migrants with insecure or irregular legal status, for whom this sector represents one of the few viable options for earning a livelihood (van Doorn et al., 2023; van Doorn & Vijay, 2024).

Several features of the sector enable this entry: minimal formal requirements, quick onboarding, and —crucially—the informal use of shared or rented accounts. For many, substitution is not a legal loophole but a survival mechanism (Mendonça et al., 2024). But this informality now sits squarely in the crosshairs of political and regulatory scrutiny. The 2024 so-called ‘Deliveroo Visa scandal’, in which over 100 riders were terminated for using substitute accounts, catalysed public anxiety about ‘illegal working’ in the sector (Barr, 2025; Timothy & Penn, 2025). In March 2025, Labour’s Home Secretary Yvette Cooper announced new compliance requirements for platforms, including more rigorous right-to-work checks through mandatory daily biometric identity verification and restrictions on device and account sharing (Home Office & Cooper, 2025; Seddon, 2025).

These measures are now fully operational. As of June 2025, riders must verify their identity multiple times per day, use only one registered device, and formally register substitute riders. As our fieldwork activities took place precisely throughout these important changes in identity recognition processes, we had the opportunity to observe how these changes have disrupted the informal infrastructures on which many precarious migrant workers depend and excluded many riders from the sector. For undocumented riders or those caught in long and opaque immigration processes, the risk of being deactivated or exposed to immigration enforcement has grown sharply.

Meanwhile, enforcement has expanded from digital to physical space, with the new regime coinciding with a surge in workplace immigration raids targeting delivery riders (Wall, 2024). In Birmingham, where this research is based, these developments are also shaped by local narratives about ‘dangerous e-bikes’ and ‘pavement riding’, further stigmatising food delivery workers and reinforcing their visibility as a perceived public nuisance or threat (Better Streets for Birmingham, 2025; Birmingham City Council, 2024; Walker, 2025).

In this shifting environment, the food delivery sector has become a testing ground for new forms of digital labour regulation and immigration control. What emerges is a hybrid regime: algorithmic discipline meets border enforcement; legal ambiguity meets technological scrutiny. These dynamics do not operate in abstraction. As the following sections show, they fundamentally shape the working conditions, legal risks, and everyday decisions of migrant workers navigating an increasingly hostile—and tightly policed—urban labour market.

3. Methodology and sample

The study was conducted between January and April 2025 in Birmingham, the UK's second-largest city (population: 1,144,900). Birmingham represents a significant case study due to its ethnic diversity, with over 40% of residents from Black and Minority Ethnic (BME) backgrounds, with significant communities from South Asia (27%) and notably diverse religious landscape, with Christians (34%) and Muslims (30%) forming the largest faith groups (Birmingham City Council, 2021).

The city also faces considerable socioeconomic challenges. The unemployment rate (8.7%) is double the UK average, while household overcrowding affects over 10% of residents—triple the national average (Birmingham City Council, 2021). According to the Indices of Multiple Deprivation, more than 60% of Birmingham's population resides in the most deprived areas of the country, with significant spatial inequality across neighbourhoods (Birmingham City Council, 2019).

This demographic landscape has significant implications for migrant workers. While high unemployment and deprivation levels may drive more people toward gig economy work, established migrant communities and a robust migrant support infrastructure through numerous civil society organisations provide valuable social networks and support systems for newcomers. At the same time, high-deprivation areas and urban development that prioritises cars over other transportation modes create safety and infrastructure challenges for food delivery workers.

The research methodology carried out in this context combined ethnographic observations across Birmingham with semi-structured interviews with twelve current or former migrant food delivery workers in the West Midlands. Interviews were audio-recorded and conducted online, by phone, or in person. They covered topics including migration journeys and immigration status, labour market experiences, livelihood and legal status, help and support networks, and future plans. Participants received a £30 thank-you voucher at the end of each interview to recognize the time they spent sharing their stories.

Notably, the number of participants has been affected by increased concerns over immigration enforcement. This has significantly complicated data collection, as delivery workers are now reluctant to participate in research due to fears of surveillance and legal repercussions, and has required adapting research methods to a period of heightened security concerns.

To provide broader context, we conducted expert interviews with twelve stakeholders, including a researcher specialising in platform economy, four trade unionists, three legal advisers and four migrant rights organisations. These expert interviews helped contextualise the working conditions of food delivery riders within broader debates about workers' rights in Birmingham and beyond. The research was further informed by analysis of relevant grey literature.

Observations and informal interactions with delivery riders were also conducted at various locations throughout the city, particularly at parking spots where riders take breaks near high streets in the city centre, as well as in southern and eastern districts. Additional observations and interactions took place at an asylum seekers' hotel in the city centre and outside a local organisation providing legal advice to migrant workers. Parts of the thematic analysis and drafting process were assisted by ChatGPT, a large language model developed by OpenAI. No personal or identifiable data was shared with the tool, and all inputs were anonymised in line with data protection requirements.

The research team included two research assistants with lived experience of migration and precarious immigration status, who are actively involved in migrant and worker rights organisations, with one of them having also worked in food delivery. Their experiential knowledge and familiarity with sectoral dynamics and policies were crucial in building trust with participants, conducting interviews covering potentially sensitive issues, and analysing the data in relation to broader structural conditions affecting the food delivery industry.

Migrant interviewees came from diverse backgrounds. The sample included six Brazilian participants, as well as individuals from India, Pakistan, Hong Kong, Italy, Eritrea, and France. Regarding gender distribution, the group comprised eleven male participants and one female participant—a ratio that reflects the male-dominated nature of the sector.

Moreover, they held various immigration statuses at the time of interview: British National Overseas visa, Care Worker visa, Indefinite Leave to Remain, Asylum Seeker status, and EU pre-settled status (one participant each), EU Settled Status (four participants), and overstayed visitor visas with no right to remain (three participants).

However, immigration status emerged as a dynamic rather than static condition, with many participants experiencing varying immigration statuses over time. At the more privileged end, some interviewees held EU settled or pre-settled status. However, these statuses often resulted from precarious journeys marked by bureaucratic struggles during the post-Brexit transition period or from acquisition of EU ‘ancestral’ citizenship after periods of undocumented status in the UK. At the less privileged end, we encountered individuals who had overstayed their visas, thus having no legal right to remain or work in the UK, or who were in breach of visa conditions by working outside their permitted sector because the license of their sponsor had been revoked. In between these extremes were asylum seekers and BNO visa holders, whose future right to remain depends on factors both within and beyond their control, from Home Office decisions to their ability to pay substantial visa fees.

4. Understanding the nexus between immigration status and work: empirical findings

4.1. Immigration Status and Right to Work

Migrant workers in the food delivery sector often enter the UK through varied and often complex, legal pathways shaped by personal aspiration, family dynamics, and immigration policy infrastructures (Piemontese and Sigona 2024; Sigona et al 2021). Their experiences demonstrate how immigration status is not fixed but rather a shifting and relational condition, vulnerable to bureaucratic discretion, breakdown of personal relationships, or changes in national policy.

Jamal’s case is emblematic³. Now an asylum seeker, he entered the UK on a spousal visa. After his marriage ended, his visa was revoked, leaving him without the right to remain or work. “My life depends on her, not just the Home Office”, he said, illustrating how immigration law can render personal relationships a vector of legal vulnerability. Despite eventually receiving permission to work as an asylum seeker, Jamal found that

³ All names in the report are pseudonyms. that have been either agreed upon after the interview or assigned by the research team to reflect the national, ethnic, or religious identity of the participants.

employers often denied him opportunities, citing a lack of acceptable documents. “Even though there is a legal right to work, many companies are unaware of this because they require a travel document”, he explained. The gap between formal entitlement and actual access is a recurring theme across the migrant workers we interviewed.

Others experience legal precarity in subtler but equally constraining ways. Assi, a French national originally from the Ivory Coast, is a UK long-term resident with EU citizenship and later EU settled status, and yet faced recurring demands to prove habitual residency post-Brexit. “It’s like starting over”, he recalled. His experience demonstrates how systems of surveillance and suspicion persist even for those with formal legal protection—especially for racialised migrants—undermining the presumed stability of citizenship.

Kuan, from Hong Kong, arrived under the BNO visa scheme as a dependent. Despite being university-educated, language barriers to professional employment, childcare responsibilities, and migration-related financial pressure led him into food delivery. “We need to think about how to make more money to support this... everything is unknown”, he said. This illustrates how legal status offers entry but not stability.

Some, like Rayan, are victims of visa fraud. He paid £20,000 for a sponsorship that never materialised, leaving him to survive by using his wife’s delivery account, as her dependent visa allows her to work in any sector for any employer. “I feel like a slave”, he said, underscoring how both dependency and deception compound his precarity, even with a Care Work visa in hand.

Other participants reveal also how minor bureaucratic errors can lead to years of uncertainty. Gaetano, an Italian citizen with a long history of informal employment, was rejected for EU pre-settled status after Brexit due to insufficient proof of residency. “It was in my spam folder. I didn’t even know I was rejected”, he recalled, highlighting the punitive consequences of bureaucratic opacity and digital exclusion.

George, originally from India, by contrast, had managed to secure a permanent residence permit after navigating multiple status transitions and is now in the process of applying for naturalisation. His case reflects the long-term potential of legal stability, but only after a protracted journey involving economic downgrading and familial sacrifice.

Brazilian workers in the sector further highlight how even EU citizenship does not preclude exploitation. Igor and Guilherme, who moved to the UK using Italian passports – Guilherme on a spouse visa based on his wife Italian passport – avoided direct immigration enforcement but still faced irregular hours, income volatility, and insecurity. “You need to work until midnight just to hit your goal”, Guilherme explained. Legal rights did not shield them from the disciplining effects of platform labour.

Benedito, however, remained undocumented despite several attempts to regularise his status. Working under rented accounts, he paid over £130 a week in fees for his account and hired bike before earning any income. His story mirrors others in the report marked by institutional mistrust, informal arrangements, and persistent vulnerability.

These cases collectively reveal that legal status operates less as a binary than a spectrum of inclusion and exclusion. Whether through revoked spousal visas, unrecognised EU rights, fraudulent sponsorships, or undocumented entry, migrants in the sector experience legal status as both a gatekeeper and a moving target, profoundly shaping their livelihood opportunities and sense of belonging.

4.2. Life on the Road: Precarity, Exploitation, and the Algorithm

Food delivery work is in the first place physically exhausting and mentally taxing. As Rayan explains, despite having been victim several times of traffic accidents and attempts of robbery, the main source of exhaustion is the constant physical pain he and his fellow workers go through:

Your hands are not working at -5°C, you know? Believe me, I wear four pair of socks, when I come out, four pair of socks, three trousers and up to the trousers I wear two waterproof trouser, right? And then a jacket, then another jacket [...] And after that, well, when I'm working like constantly for 8 or 9 or 10 or 12 hours, you know, sometimes I can't feel in my hands, sometimes I can't feel my fingers. [...] And then when I go home at night [...] my legs are like, you know, they are so cold that it will take, like, up to two to three hours in a heated rooms to in a heated room to get their strength back again.

Beyond the physical fatigue, the food delivery sector crystallises many of the contradictions of the broader gig economy: while advertised as flexible and empowering, it is, in practice, defined by insecurity, surveillance, and structural coercion, particularly for migrant workers.

For many, food delivery is not a preferred option but a fallback in the face of exclusion from more stable or regulated forms of employment. As Aidan, a labour rights expert and former rider, noted, the sector has transitioned from an innovation-driven model to one reliant on migrant and racialised labour, whose invisibility renders them disposable.

Algorithmic management is central to this transformation. Rather than offering autonomy, platforms use opaque and unaccountable systems to monitor, discipline, and reward workers. App-based ratings, delivery times, and customer reviews become tools of governance, shaping not only earnings but also access to work (Badger, 2021; Worker Info Exchange, 2023). Guilherme, who had worked in the sector for many years, initially as an undocumented migrant, points out that, despite his relative immigration status security now, he still faced long shifts, irregular income, and the constant threat of account suspension, mirroring the experience of many undocumented riders.

Benedito's experience exposes the deeper exploitation enabled by this system. Paying both for a substitute account and a vehicle weekly, he bore all the risk—customer complaints, accidents, poor ratings—without formal recognition or rights. The platform's power, extended through intermediaries, operated without oversight.

Algorithmic control also reconfigures the very notion of accountability. José feared delayed orders more than theft; Giovanna, after a crash, was off work for 10 days but never reported the accident to her company because she explains: "I didn't even try because I'd seen so many people get injured and end up with nothing. Honestly, I didn't even think about it at the time. I just wanted to get better".

During his 3-year career as a food delivery rider, first in London and then in Birmingham, Gaetano's account was suspended three times due to late food deliveries and delayed bicycle returns to the hub. In his opinion, these issues were more related to the company's delivery organization than his performance.

Algorithmic management also produces new forms of "soft discipline". José, whose motorcycle was stolen during a delivery, explained that his biggest fear was not the theft itself, but the risk that delayed orders would result in penalties or deactivation. Mario described how a minor disagreement with a restaurant

about a pickup led to a cascade of negative outcomes, including a threat of account suspension. In both cases, automated systems amplified vulnerability by treating disruption—whether caused by theft, weather, or simple human error—as worker failure.

The opacity of these systems—how decisions are made, how ratings are calculated, what leads to account deactivation—deepens the asymmetry between platforms and workers. Igor and Guilherme both reported being ‘ghosted’ by the platform after accidents, receiving no support or explanation, only to find their accounts deactivated or deprioritised. As Igor put it, “you just disappear... the app stops giving you jobs, and you don’t know why.”

While framed as neutral or efficient, algorithmic control is not evenly distributed. It intersects with legal status, race, and linguistic barriers to further marginalise those least equipped to navigate the system. Benedito and José, both working informally or semi-formally, lacked access to platform support systems entirely, depending instead on peer advice and WhatsApp groups. This reinforces the emergence of an informal knowledge economy in which migrants train and manage each other, stepping in where platforms remain opaque or indifferent.

Ultimately, algorithmic control in the food delivery sector doesn’t just structure work: it also helps enforce a hierarchy of precarity, where those without stable legal status, fluent English, or digital literacy are kept at the bottom. Migrants, regardless of citizenship or rights on paper, are rendered functionally expendable through these systems, which offer no path for appeal or negotiation. As one rider put it, “You are working for a machine, and you never know if you’re doing it right until the money stops coming”.

Jamal described how even when earning only £4, he waited for hours to return undelivered food to a restaurant. “If I don’t do it and go home, my account will be closed”, he said. This illustrates the power of algorithmic control and the platform’s rigid procedures, which often prioritise customer service over worker safety.

Kuan echoed this anxiety. His motorcycle was stolen by a group of robbers, leaving him traumatised and income-less for two weeks. “I was scared... after this case happened, I didn’t do delivery maybe for two weeks. No income. I was scared walking at the nighttime. The sky is dark at 3pm”. After speaking with a friend and slowly rebuilding confidence, he resumed deliveries, but avoids the location of the robbery and has decided to stop using a motorcycle.

Giovanna, a Brazilian national and former logistics professional, turned to platform-based delivery work after migrating to the UK. At first, she appreciated the job’s flexibility and the immediate access to income. However, over time, she faced the structural vulnerabilities of gig work. After a motorcycle accident that left her unable to work for days without any financial support, and repeated incidents involving customer aggression during ID checks, she began to feel increasingly unsafe. Although she reported some of these episodes to the platforms, her concerns were often dismissed or blamed on her: “I reported it, but sometimes they said I was the one who treated the customer badly, even though it was the customer who mistreated me”. Giovanna’s experience reveals how occupational risk, gendered safety concerns, and institutional neglect converge in the gig economy, especially for migrant women delivery workers.

Assi’s early experience in the food delivery sector echoes the systemic pressures that lead migrants to engage in informal practices, such as account sharing or borrowing. After losing formal employment during the pandemic, he borrowed a scooter and used a friend’s delivery app account to survive.

The ‘substitution clause’, allowing registered couriers to subcontract deliveries, is often blamed for creating a thriving grey market for account borrowing and rental. However, this informal market would likely persist even in the absence of such provision – as the recent pressures to enhance identity checks without eliminating the ‘substitution clause’ suggest. While these tactics sometimes result from solidarity among friends and extended family members, the reality is more complex: fees are high, working conditions poor, and coercion common. As Teodoro, a trade unionist and private hire driver, put it, “People with fake documents or rented accounts work longer, harder. But if anything happens, account gone. No rights, no appeal”.

However, to many respondents, the substitution clause—which often requires paying to use another person's account—represents just another financial burden among many imposed by companies (such as mandatory accident insurance) and governments (including high visa fees). In other words, claims about migrants being victimized by account-renting gangs are only valid if we also acknowledge the extractive fees charged by companies, insurers, and governments.

As we write, the enhanced identity checks performed by platform companies have created new forms of vulnerabilities whose emerging impact needs to be further investigated. The most likely consequences are the exclusion of migrants with precarious immigration status from a sector that provided a precarious yet accessible source of income, and the restructuring of substitute account borrowing systems, leading to increased fees and other forms of exploitation and dependency.

Despite these pressures, some moments of relative autonomy exist. Gaetano described one brief period working with a legitimate intermediary agency as “the best time of my life”, after a long history of informal employment. Paid hourly, with a regular shift and clear procedures, he experienced a fleeting sense of stability. However, his situation underscores the fragility of even partial inclusion. After a traffic accident and his subsequent ‘erasure’ from the system –amid JustEat’s 2023 restructuring and return to a gig-economy model – he was left unable to access essential employment protections despite having payslips and a work history.

These accounts show that algorithmic governance in the gig economy does not merely shape productivity—it structures a racialised and stratified labour regime. Legal status offers no guaranteed insulation from exploitation; in many cases, it is irrelevant to how the system allocates risk and reward. In this sense, the algorithm acts as both employer and border guard, regulating who gets to work, how, and for how long.

4.3. Family, Status, and the Costs of Precarity

Though food delivery work is commonly perceived as a solitary and male-dominated occupation, its effects ripple across households, relationships, and transnational kinship networks. The intersection of legal precarity and economic insecurity reshapes family life in profound and uneven ways.

For some, immigration status becomes a site of intimate power struggles. Jamal's wife used her sponsorship role as leverage during the breakdown of their relationship: “She said, I have the right to cancel your visa and can send you back home”. Here, immigration law functions not just as state control but as a domestic weapon, turning private relationships into legal battlegrounds.

For others, like Kuan, work-life decisions are constrained by care responsibilities. As a father and dependent visa holder, he must structure his deliveries around school runs and household tasks. “£50 the whole day. Why? Because I need to take the kid, do homework, cook dinner”. His income is not just shaped by platform logic but by the rhythms of family life, with no institutional support to bridge the two.

Rayan, defrauded out of a visa sponsorship, now bears the financial burden of supporting a growing family, serving as the main breadwinner while his wife cares for their toddler. His precarious legal status creates tension with the responsibility of being a breadwinner, intensifying feelings of vulnerability and stress. “Every day is a hustle”, he said. The weight of transnational expectations, coupled with local precarity, generates a constant emotional strain.

Some migrants seek escape from these constraints not through upward mobility in the UK but through onward migration. Giovanna, who faced occupational risks and a lack of institutional support while working without legal status in the UK, relocated to Spain after obtaining European citizenship. There, she found employment in her professional field. Her case illustrates how, even when legal status is eventually secured, it does not necessarily lead to a sense of safety, stability, or belonging in the UK context.

Others, like Assi, remain, caught in a cycle of overwork and responsibility. Despite citizenship, he struggles to support his nuclear family in the UK and extended family abroad: “How can you save when what you earn is not enough for here and you have to feed mouths back home?”.

Family life is further strained by the long hours and physical risks of delivery work. George, now more secure, reflected on the toll of earlier years: “I spent too many hours away from my family”. His later move to part-time work as a school coach driver was motivated as much by the desire for presence as by income stability.

Benedito and José’s cases link insecure work to unstable housing. With no fixed contracts or regular income, they navigate exploitative rental arrangements, temporary housing, and constant moves. Benedito feared calling an ambulance after a delivery accident, worried that contact with public services might expose his undocumented status. These conditions reflect a broader structural pattern: legal precarity in the workplace feeds into housing insecurity and health risks, while discouraging recourse to public institutions.

Even those with status, like Guilherme and Igor, reported repeated motorbike accidents and were not given adequate recovery support by the platforms. Instead, they relied on migrant-run repair shops to stay on the road. These accounts confirm that legal status does not equal protection, either from occupational harm or from the broader systems of marginalisation that shape life in the UK.

Stakeholder interviews echo these insights. Many noted that remittance pressures are not diminishing but intensifying, even as local conditions deteriorate. Migrants are squeezed between multiple obligations, and with little institutional buffer. Family life, rather than providing relief from precarity, becomes another domain where its effects are felt most acutely.

4.4. Structures of Silence and the Limits of Support

Mistrust of formal institutions is a defining feature of migrants’ navigation of both immigration and labour regimes. Despite facing acute vulnerabilities, many workers avoid engagement with unions, or support organisations – or are simply unaware they exist (see Mendonça et al., 2024). This stems partly from Birmingham’s position as a peripheral city compared to London regarding delivery worker unionisation efforts – a situation made worse by both the Supreme Court’s ruling that limited unions’ ability to represent these workers and the emerging criminalization narrative.

Jamal never contacted a lawyer after his visa was revoked. Instead, he followed the advice of friends. Others echoed this strategy: “They don’t fully trust them” a community mediator explained. This avoidance is not rooted in ignorance but in the calculated perception that institutions offer little support—and may even pose risks.

Even when migrants engage with civil society actors, they may self-censor. Aidan, a labour rights researcher and former delivery rider, noted that some migrants withhold details of labour exploitation from support organisations because they know these are not grounds for legal protection. Silence, in this sense, becomes a form of strategic self-preservation. We have observed similar attitudes during our ethnographic interactions and recruitment efforts, pointing to deep-seated mistrust and fear of immigration enforcement in an increasingly hostile environment.

Trade unions are often perceived as irrelevant or ineffective. George expressed disappointment at the lack of assistance when his account was suspended. Kuan associated unions with cleaning work, not the self-employed. For trade unionists like Teodoro, unions’ partnerships with platforms amount to complicity: “A slap in the face of the worker”, he said of collective agreements that failed to address core issues.

The fear of detection further discourages formal engagement. Aidan recounted cases where workers were arrested after being invited to supposed workplace ‘meetings’—collusion between immigration enforcement and employers that confirmed long-standing suspicions among migrant communities.

Instead, workers rely on informal networks. Kuan turns first to other Hong Kong migrants. Rayan mentors newer riders, including asylum seekers, on how to register bank accounts and navigate app procedures. These acts of everyday solidarity function as a replacement for institutional support.

Gaetano’s turning point came only after intervention from a caseworker, which allowed him to secure pre-settled status. “Without that letter, I would be homeless”, he said. His case illustrates that support can be transformative, but access to it remains arbitrary and contingent.

Platforms themselves are seen as indifferent at best, exploitative at worst. After being robbed, Kuan received no support from the app. “Everything is about yourself”, he said. Even onboarding, once free, now comes with costs. “£40 for a background check. Just another way to make money from migrants”, he said

Even prominent community leaders are not spared. Assi, founder of a migrant support organisation, received death threats linked to his advocacy. The police refused to investigate due to “lack of evidence”. His story reveals how civic participation does not shield migrants from neglect, and may even expose them to new forms of harm.

Together, these accounts point to a vacuum of institutional trust. Migrants navigate risk not only in work and status, but in choosing when and whether to seek help. In this vacuum, informal solidarity becomes both lifeline and burden, with community members picking up the slack of absent or indifferent systems.

4.5. The Future: Endurance, Stagnation, and Ambivalence

Migrant workers' views of the future oscillate between resignation and aspiration, often shaped by the depth of their legal insecurity and the limitations of gig work.

George, having achieved a permanent residence permit and property ownership, represents a trajectory of hard-won stability. His current goal is naturalisation. But his story also reflects years of economic and social compromise.

Jamal, in contrast, remains suspended in uncertainty. "There isn't much I can do to improve the situation," he said. His legal limbo translates into emotional paralysis and constrained planning.

Teodoro captures the broader structural context: "The government sees delivery workers as undignified persons". Aidan adds: "The platforms are learning how to play the political game... but it's unfortunate for workers". These insights point to a labour regime where workers are seen as expendable, their rights hollowed out by legal ambiguity and algorithmic control.

Igor's experience shows that, in rare cases, food delivery can serve as a platform for transition. By combining delivery work with studies in programming and data science, he secured a junior role in tech. The new job came with lower initial pay but offered stable hours and a sense of purpose. He explains his transition:

I definitely weighed the risks: accidents, theft. It reached a point where I said, "this doesn't make sense anymore". [...] Emotionally, I was very involved with delivery work... but then reason kicked in. [...] I had already completed a data engineering course, and I wasn't even working in the field. I thought: "I've done this course, it's been six months, and I'm still not in tech – what am I doing?"

His story is an outlier—but it suggests that when given room to manoeuvre, migrants can mobilise networks and educational resources to imagine alternative futures.

Yet for most, food delivery is a site not of transition but of entrapment. Their accounts reflect not only economic exhaustion but social disillusionment. As one stakeholder said, "This is a system designed to benefit from people's silence".

Despite the weight of these constraints, many participants displayed remarkable endurance. As Kuan put it: "Here, I try to keep things simple. Work, family, survive". This ethos—stoic yet fragile—captures the mood of many: suspended between dreams deferred and daily survival.

5. Conclusion

The experiences of migrant workers in the food delivery sector reveal more than individual hardship; they expose a labour regime that depends on the marginality and silence of migrant workers. Legal status, far from being a stable category, emerges as a deeply relational and conditional position—one that intersects with race, class, gender, and digital access to structure vulnerability which reverberates in the lives of workers and their families.

In the food delivery industry, where algorithmic control increasingly intersects with immigration enforcement, migrant workers sit at the frontier of digital bordering—caught in webs of exploitation,

exclusion, and precarious livelihoods. Gig work offers autonomy in name but embeds dependency on opaque systems and faceless algorithms. For many, food delivery is not a stepping stone, but a trap.

While the gig economy promises flexibility and opportunity, the lived realities reveal a system built on instability, surveillance, and exclusion. The platform's digital infrastructure thus becomes an informal extension of the border regime—sorting, disciplining, and, when necessary, ejecting workers.

These accounts show that precarity is not only economic, but social and structural—shaping educational outcomes, family dynamics, civic participation, and emotional wellbeing. The Brazilian cases, in particular, illuminate the distinction between irregular status and structural precarity. While some participants are undocumented, others possess full EU citizenship or settled status. Yet across these legal categories, they share common experiences: algorithmic exploitation, informal labour practices, occupational risk, and housing insecurity.

Crucially, this research highlights the structural alignment between immigration control and the architecture of gig capitalism. Immigration policies generate gradients of legal precarity, while platform systems—through opaque algorithms translate these gradients into hierarchies of labour. As one stakeholder put it, “This is a system designed to benefit from people’s silence”. Migrant workers are often legal enough to be useful, but not legal enough to be protected.

In this system, migrants’ vulnerability is not incidental—it is rather produced, maintained, and monetised. The gig economy does not merely reflect existing inequalities; it actively reproduces them. And yet, within these constraints, migrants also demonstrate remarkable endurance and agency. As Kuan said, “Here, I try to keep things simple. Work, family, survive”.

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